

Proof of Twin prime conjecture

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Lemma1

All prime numbers greater than or equal to 5 can be expressed as two forms:

$$6k - 1$$
$$6k + 1$$

Pf)

All natural numbers are expressed by

$$6k, 6k+1, 6k+2, 6k+3, 6k+4, 6k+5$$

$6k$ is a multiple of 6.

$6k+2=2(3k+1)$ is a multiple of 2.

$6k+3=3(2k+1)$ is a multiple of 3.

$6k+4=2(3k+2)$ is a multiple of 2.

$6k+5=6(k+1)-1$ is the form of $(6k-1)$.

Therefore, the only two possible forms that could be prime are
 $(6k - 1), (6k + 1)$

For some natural number m , if $(6m-1)$ and $(6m+1)$ is all prime numbers at the same time, these two numbers are twin primes.

$$\text{Ex) } 11 = 6 \times 2 - 1, 13 = 6 \times 2 + 1$$

11,13 are twin primes.

Lemma2.

The product of $(6k - 1)$ or $(6k + 1)$ are again in the form of $(6k' - 1)$ or $(6k' + 1)$

pf)

(i)

$$\begin{aligned}(6k - 1) \times (6m - 1) &= 36km - 6k - 6m + 1 \\ &= 6(6km - k - m) + 1 = 6k' + 1\end{aligned}$$

(ii)

$$\begin{aligned}(6k - 1) \times (6m + 1) &= 36km + 6k - 6m - 1 \\ &= 6(6km + k - m) - 1 = 6k' - 1\end{aligned}$$

(iii)

$$\begin{aligned}(6k + 1) \times (6m - 1) &= 36km - 6k + 6m - 1 \\ &= 6(6km - k + m) - 1 = 6k' - 1\end{aligned}$$

(iv)

$$\begin{aligned}(6k + 1) \times (6m + 1) &= 36km + 6k + 6m + 1 \\ &= 6(6km + k + m) + 1 = 6k' + 1\end{aligned}$$

It can be inductively proven that no matter how many times this form is multiplied, it will take the same form again.

Let's define {younger brother set}, and {older brother set}

Younger brother set $Y = \{k \in \mathbb{N} \mid 6k - 1\}$

That is,

Younger brother set=
 $\{5, 11, 17, 23, 29, 35, 41, 47, 53, 59, 65 \dots\}$

Older brother set $O = \{k \in \mathbb{N} \mid 6k + 1\}$

That is,

Older brother set=
 $\{7, 13, 19, 25, 31, 37, 43, 49, 55, 61, 67 \dots\}$

And let's think about union of these two sets

$$U = \{Y \cup O\}$$

By Lemma1 and Lemma2, If you multiply any elements of a set U, it will belong to U again.

This set has properties similar to a
'group'.

In other words, the elements of U are a candidates that could become twin prime numbers.

Let any element of $U = u_i$

If u_i is excluded from the prime number, the reason is that

$$u_i = u_j \times u_k$$

For example,

$$55 = 5 \times 11$$

And 5,11 are the elements of U . And also 55 is a element of U .

$$55 = 6 \times 9 + 1$$

Therefore,

$$53 = 6 \times 9 - 1$$

53, 55 are eliminated from twin prime numbers.

We can find patterns of elimination.

Let

Twin Field: a field in which the elements of U are stretched out

(i) Elimination by 5

Let's think about

$$5 \times \{\textit{Younger brother set}\}$$

That is,

$$5 \times \{5, 11, 13, 23 \dots\}$$

$$= 25, 55, 85, 115 \dots$$

We can find pattern. There's always difference of 30.

And let's look at the parameters of Twin Field, k .

$$25 = 6 \times 4 + 1$$

$$55 = 6 \times 9 + 1$$

$$85 = 6 \times 14 + 1$$

$$115 = 6 \times 19 + 1$$

\vdots

All of these are in the form of $(6k + 1)$

And let's pay attention to the parameters k .

$$k = 4, 9, 14, 19 \dots$$

It looks the form of

$$k = 5m - 1$$

How can we prove it?

It is simple.

$$5 \times (6m - 1) = 30m - 5$$

$$= 30m - 6 + 1 = 6(5m - 1) + 1$$

Therefore, in the form

$$5 \times (6m - 1) = 6k + 1 \text{ (by lemma2)}$$

$$6k + 1 = 6 \times (5m - 1) + 1,$$

$$k = 5m - 1$$

k is the parameter of the twin field, so all numbers corresponding to

$$k = 5m - 1$$

are excluded from the twin primes.

(ii)

$$5 \times \{\text{Older brother set}\}$$

$$5 \times (6m + 1) = 30m + 5 = 30m + 6 - 1 = 6(5m + 1) - 1$$

Therefore, in the form

$$6k - 1 = 6 \times (5m + 1) - 1$$

$$k = 5m + 1$$

All parameter numbers corresponding to

$$k = 5m + 1$$

are excluded from the twin primes.

Combining (i) and (ii),

For the parameter of Twin Field, k ,

$$k = 5m \pm 1$$

Are excluded from the twin primes.

Similar patterns can be found in the elements of Twin Field as well, not just 5.

$$7 \times (6m - 1) = 42m - 7 = 42m - 6 - 1 = 6(7m - 1) - 1$$

$$k_1 = 7m - 1$$

$$7 \times (6m + 1) = 42m + 7 = 42m + 6 + 1 = 6(7m + 1) - 1$$

$$k_2 = 7m + 1$$

Combining k_1, k_2 ,

$$k = 7m \pm 1$$

Are excluded from the twin primes.

Generalization

Elements of $Y = (6n-1)$ (fixed)

Product to elements of $Y=(6m-1)$

$$\begin{aligned}(6n - 1) \times (6m - 1) &= 6(6nm - m) - 6n + 1 \\ &= 6(6nm - n - m) + 1 = 6\{m(6n - 1) - n\} + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$k_1 = (6n - 1)m - n$$

Elements of $Y=(6n-1)$ (fixed)

Product to elements of $O=6m+1$

$$\begin{aligned}(6n - 1) \times (6m + 1) &= 36nm + 6n - 6m - 1 \\ &= 6(6nm + n - m) - 1 = 6\{m(6n - 1) + n\} - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$k_2 = (6n - 1)m + n$$

Combining k_1, k_2

$$k = (6n - 1)m \pm n$$

For example, $17 = 6 \times 3 - 1$

Elements of the Twin Field eliminated by 17

$$k = 17m \pm 3$$

Elements of $O = (6n+1)$ (fixed)

Product to elements of $Y = (6m-1)$

$$\begin{aligned}(6n + 1) \times (6m - 1) &= 36nm - 6n + 6m - 1 \\ &= 6(6nm - n + m) - 1 = 6\{m(6n + 1) - n\} - 1\end{aligned}$$

$$k_1 = (6n + 1)m - n$$

Elements of $O = (6n+1)$ (fixed)

Product to elements of $O = (6m+1)$

$$\begin{aligned}(6n + 1) \times (6m + 1) &= 36nm + 6n + 6m + 1 \\ &= 6(6nm + n + m) + 1 = 6 \times \{m(6n + 1) + n\} + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$k_2 = (6n + 1)m + n$$

Combining k_1, k_2

$$k = (6n + 1)m \pm n$$

EX) $31 = 6 \times 5 + 1$

Elements of the Twin Field that eliminated by 31

$$k = 31m \pm 5$$

In summary,

k=1	5	7
k=2	11	13
k=3	17	19
k=4	23	25
k=5	29	31
k=6	35	37
k=7	41	43
k=8	47	49
k=9	53	55
k=10	59	61

⋮

$k = 5m \pm 1 = 4, 6, 9, 11 \dots$ *exclude*.

Let's call this sequence $\rho(5)$

$k = 7m \pm 1 = 6, 8, 13, 15 \dots$ *exclude*. $\rho(7)$

$k = 11m \pm 2 = 9, 13, 20, 24 \dots$ *exclude* $\rho(11)$

$k = 13m \pm 2 = 11, 15, 24, 26 \dots$ *exclude* $\rho(13)$

⋮

Therefore this is the question.

These sequences $\rho(5), \rho(7), \rho(11), \rho(13) \dots$ can exclude all k , the parameter of the Twin Field?

However, there are duplicate numbers in these sequences.

But we ignore it and let's find the minimum remaining ratio.

$\rho(5)$: period 5, 2 exclude \rightarrow The average remaining proportion among k up to N is

$$\frac{3}{5} N$$

$\rho(7)$: period 7, 2 exclude. Average remaining proportion $\frac{5}{7}$

$\rho(11)$: period 11, 2 edclude. Average remaining proportion $\frac{9}{11}$

\vdots

The minimum remaining ratio:

$$\frac{3}{5} \times \frac{5}{7} \times \frac{9}{11} \times \frac{11}{13} \times \frac{15}{17} \times \frac{17}{19} \times \frac{21}{23} \times \frac{23}{25} \times \frac{27}{29} \times \frac{29}{31} \times \dots$$

We can simplify it and if the number of twin primes is finite, this minimum must be diverge to finite number.

Then, we have to notice two facts:

1. For some natural number q ,

Too big number q cannot exclude the number k less than or equal to N .

For example,

$$\rho(11) = 11m \pm 2 = 9, 13, 20, 24 \dots$$

Since m is a natural numbers,

$\rho(11)$ cannot exclude the number k which is less than 9.

$$\rho(25) = 25m \pm 4 = 21, 29, 46, 54 \dots$$

$\rho(25)$ cannot exclude the number k which is less than 21.

Therefore if we examine the natural numbers k less than 21, we don't need to product ratio $\rho(q)$, which is $q > 25$.

2.

$$7 \times 13 = 13 \times 7 = 91 = 6 \times 15 + 1$$

Product of 7 and 13 is equal to product of 13 and 7.

Therefore, if we examine until $k \leq 15$,

we don't need to product the ratio of $\rho(13)$.

Because it is already eliminated by 5,7, which is the Twin Field number less than 13.

In general, if we examine the exclude Twin Field number k up to N ,

It is sufficient to product the ratio $\rho(q)$ which satisfies

$$q \leq \sqrt{6N + 1}$$

Now, use this fact, if we calculate the minimum number of k up to N that will not be eliminated, for $q \leq \sqrt{6N + 1}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{minimum} &= N \times \frac{3}{5} \times \frac{5}{7} \times \frac{9}{11} \times \frac{11}{13} \times \frac{15}{17} \times \dots \times \frac{q-2}{q} > N \times \frac{3}{q} \\ &\geq N \times \frac{3}{\sqrt{6N+1}} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore the number of k which is not eliminated is greater than $\frac{3N}{\sqrt{6N+1}}$ for all N .

If the number of twin primes is finite,

$$\frac{3N}{\sqrt{6N + 1}}$$

must diverge to a finite number even if the value of N increases.

But

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \text{infinite}} \frac{3N}{\sqrt{6N + 1}} = \text{infinite}$$

The minimum number of twin primes is not finite as N increases.

If we assume that twin primes is finite, it is contradiction.

As a result, the number of twin primes is infinite.

Plus: How can we be sure that

$$N \times \frac{3}{5} \times \frac{5}{7} \times \frac{9}{11} \times \dots$$

is the minimum?

If $N=6$ and $q = 5$

$$6 \times \frac{3}{5} = 3.6$$

It is not natural number. And the actual number remaining is 4.

Therefore

$$(\text{actual})4 > N \times \frac{3}{5} = 3.6 \text{ (formula)}$$

Does it always hold true?

Yes. Because in the sequence $\rho(5) = 5m \pm 1$,

we ignored the $m=0$. It is 1.

So 1 is not eliminated, no matter what N comes, even if it is decimal, there is one leftover, so the actual remaining number is larger than the calculated value by the formula.

Plus 2)

Why 'not eliminated k' is always prime number?

Because if any composite number S is factorized, it is always factorized by prime number.

And prime number is 2,3,5,7...

All prime numbers except 2,3 are always on the Twin Field.

And any $(6k-1)$ and $(6k+1)$ are not a multiple of 2 or 3.

And Twin Field is closed under product.

Therefore, if any number on the Twin Field is a composite number, it is always factorized into elements of Twin Field.

And a product of Twin Field is always on the sequence

$$\rho(5), \rho(7), \rho(11), \rho(13) \dots$$

So any 'not eliminated k' is always make twin primes

$$(6k - 1), (6k + 1)$$

Thank you for reading.